

The Importance Of Social Sciences In The Life Of Our Country Today

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Abstract: *this article will talk about the current role of the social sciences and the reforms carried out in the direction of the social sciences and their effectiveness. In which areas exactly the social sciences are important and the reasons for it are analyzed. At the same time, scientifically based conclusions of problems and solutions to them in this area, which are considered relevant today, are described.*

Keywords — society, ideology, Renaissance, humanism, anthropology, archaeology, sociology, psychology.

INTRODUCTION.

Science is a system of knowledge about the world, one of the forms of social consciousness. It includes activities related to the acquisition of new knowledge, as well as the product of this activity - the knowledge that forms the basis of the scientific view of the world; represents some areas of human knowledge. The direct goal of science is to describe, explain and predict the processes and events of this reality based on the discovery of the laws of the reality that is the subject of its study. The fields of science are studied in three large groups. They are:

Natural sciences, exact sciences and social sciences.

To understand what social science is, it is necessary to first answer the question of what society is. Because the basis of the word social is society. Society can mean different things. But when we say society, we mainly think of a group of people. In fact, society is the union of people on the basis of a common goal. Society cannot exist without people. So, based on this, we can say that social sciences are a set of sciences related to society and human behavior. We can mention several social sciences:

- Anthropology is the science of human origin and evolution, normal differences in human body structure, and variability.
- Archeology is a science that studies the past of human society based on the monuments of ancient material culture.
- Sociology is the science of society as a whole system and of certain social orders, processes, social groups, and relations between individuals and society.
- History is a science related to the collection, organization and presentation of information about past events.
- Jurisprudence is a science that studies separate branches of law, state and separate branches of law, the history of state and law, and the activity of the political system in general as a separate system of legal and social norms.

• Psychology is the science of mental reflection of reality, mental processes, situations, events, feelings in the process of human activity and animal behavior.

• The science of psychic reflection of reality, mental processes, situations, events, feelings in the process of human activity and animal behavior. The research subject of psychology includes such psychological processes and categories as sensations and images of perception, thinking and feeling, activity and behavior.

If we look at the history of the origin of social sciences, we can see that it has a long past. We would not be mistaken if we say that social sciences have been formed since ancient times. For example, Socrates, Demosthenes, Herodotus and other scientists tried to describe the psychology of humanity and did a lot of work on it. As a clear example of this, we can cite the work of Herodotus "History". We can interpret this work of Herodotus not only as a historical chronicle, but also as a classification of people's thoughts and worldview of that time. Later, during the renaissance, attention to social sciences increased. Also, the term humanism appeared and began to be widely used from the 14th century. The word humanism brought to life the terms of glorification of man and humanity. Humanists believed in the unlimited power of man. That is why this period is called the renaissance period. Awakening is not only a period of declaration of a perfect personality, but also not a striving for an ideal, but its true embodiment. This period created a number of wonderful people who are well-educated, brilliantly talented, goal-oriented, hardworking and have great energy. Leonardo da Vinci, Raphael Santi, Michelangelo, Albrecht Dürer, Niccolò Machiavelli, Martin Luther are the most prominent representatives of the Renaissance. In this way, social sciences were born and developed.

Nowadays, these sciences have a great place in people's lives. If we take psychology as an example, now the whole world is trying to innovate in this science. In addition to the growing number of problems such as international disputes, political pressures, environmental problems, lack of resources, these problems also affect human psychology. Due to this, psychological diseases are on the rise, especially among young

people. To prevent this, psychologists are conducting many experiments. In addition, the increase in the number of crimes such as drug and human trafficking also requires the development of social sciences, in particular, the field of international jurisprudence. In short, it serves as a basis for building immunity against crimes such as religious extremism and terrorism.

All this should be true for school or university students, because the ability to think, generalize, filter incoming information and communicate in the 21st century is necessary for all professionals. In modern society, the role of the subjectivity of the individual is increasing both to organize his own life and to unite the efforts of specialists in solving professional problems and management problems.

Also, the development of social sciences can lead to the improvement of relations between the people and the government. As a result of the development of social consciousness, the scope of human thinking expands. Humanistic ethics are necessary to regulate relations in modern society. The famous German sociologist E. Fromm says: "The individual himself creates, regulates and applies laws and norms." This is a necessary feature of modern human consciousness.

The 20th century was recorded in the history of the development of human society as a period of revolutions in the field of science and technology. This period brought many inventions and discoveries in the field of science and at the same time, it also started significant changes in the world of politics. As much as this period was rich in historical events in the history of the world, it also left a deep mark in the history of Uzbekistan. The greatest and noblest gift of the 20th century to the people of our country was the achievement of the independence of the national state of Uzbekistan. Because freedom from the oppression and oppression of colonialism, achieving independence in the literal sense was the long-awaited dream of our people. Thousands of children of the nation sacrificed their lives for this goal. The independence of the national state of Uzbekistan, the great happiness of our people living free, free, self-determining and deciding their own destiny has been given to the representatives of today's generation.

Attention to social sciences is also increasing in our country. In particular, many innovations are introduced in the field of law. Because it must be recognized that the field of law and legislation needs reforms. In particular, it is necessary to increase the legal literacy and legal culture of the population. For this, it is necessary to increase the hours of social studies at school, not to be limited only to theory, to explain how important a person's place in society is. It is a pity that not only schoolchildren, but also graduates of higher education institutions do not have sufficient knowledge of human sciences such as law and psychology. This has a negative impact on the structure of society and the formation of its ideology.

But reforms are being carried out in our country for the development of social sciences. On January 20, 2021, Shavkat

Miromonovich Mirziyoyev gave a speech about the lagging behind the development of social and humanitarian sciences. "Social and humanitarian sciences are of great importance in the development of our national spirituality and instilling it in the life of our people, especially our youth. Unfortunately, the development of these sciences lags behind the times. In particular, the science of history, which is extremely relevant for us, is no exception. Scientific research works on history are mainly conducted in narrative and journalistic methods. As a result, the nature of many events in our distant and recent past, the factors that caused them, and historical laws remain unexplained. We must all deeply understand one truth: national history must be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. We need to teach our youth to learn from history, to draw conclusions, to arm them with the science of history and historical thinking. For this, first of all, I think it's time to develop the concept of development of the science of history in Uzbekistan until 2030. The Institute of History should be designated as a base scientific institution for the development of this science," said the President.

The place and role of the mass media in regularly covering the process of teaching social sciences in HEIs, showing the achievements and shortcomings in this regard and fully revealing the history of our country is incomparable. There is no such force as history, philosophy, and spiritual sciences that sow the seeds of goodness in the human mind and thinking, learn from mistakes, and become beacons for creating a bright future.

At the same time, under the influence of someone's subjective approach in this direction, there are frequent cases related to the introduction of a subject and the loss of another, the addition of departments and the excessive number of professors and teachers in them. "Experiments", social science scientists and experts, professors-teachers' constant low attitude to work have caused serious damage to the field.

Several reforms have been initiated to prevent such problems in our country. As a clear example of this, we can cite the launch of the "History of Uzbekistan" TV channel. In addition, in order to prevent the shortage of qualified personnel in the field of law, the Faculty of Law was opened at the State National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent State Transport University and several other universities. This is a sign that attention has begun to be paid to the sciences related to society. Sciences such as psychology, law and philosophy are the basis of the social state. The social state means, first of all, equal opportunities for the realization of human potential, creation of necessary conditions for people to live a decent life. This is reflected in the quality of education and medicine, the development of science and culture, and the lives of young people.

In conclusion, it can be said that social sciences have an important impact on the life of every person. Every person, whether he is a politician or a statesman, or an ordinary person, is responsible and important for society. That is why social sciences are so important especially in today's rapidly developing world. In the era of globalization, protecting young people from moral threats is the task of moral education. At the

same time, today's rapid penetration of European culture and errors in its practical application are evidence of insufficient knowledge of social sciences..

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